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Automation–Augmentation Entanglement: Self-Service Technology as Driver for Change

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ABSTRACT Although the automation of work is not new, advancements in artificial intelligence, worker shortages, and the Covid-19 pandemic have accelerated recent debates. Especially in service sectors, traditional service delivery is gradually merging with machine components, requiring organizations to rethink models of service delivery. Since the adoption of self-service technology (SST) grows, users benefit from improved access and self-management without human touchpoint, yet the impact of SST on workers requires further exploration. While technology-enabled workplace transformation is well researched, unified frameworks and strategies are missing to understand the interplay of augmentation and automation as SST becomes a ubiquitous component of service. Through an integrative review we explore most cited and most recent literature on automation, augmentation, and SST. In total, we review 41 articles. This review provides a status quo on the topics automation, augmentation, and SST. Providing a combined lens, five emerging themes are discovered for future research: Social (A)symmetries, Competing Intelligences, Redistributed Responsibilities and New Skills, Merging Spaces and New Ecosystems, Governance and Ethics. This article provides an interdisciplinary review of service automation, extends previous scholarly work, and encourages new pathways for hybrid service delivery. Furthermore, embedded in the concept of a human-centered Industry 5.0, we suggest automation–augmentation entanglement as holistic framework reflecting the interplay of human and technology in the workplace.

INDEX TERMS service automation; industry 5.0; augmented work; self-service technology; artificial intelligence; integrative review

I. INTRODUCTION

Although automation has been around for decades, the concept and our understanding of it is undergoing a gradual shift. While digital technologies reengineer various tasks whereby moving task responsibility from human worker to machine, increasingly more tasks are affected [1]. With recent developments in artificial intelligence (AI) the possibilities to automate are growing, driving the debate of how automated processes will merge with and alongside human workers [2]. Since the first industrial revolution, the role of technology and workers has been shifting, gradually

evolving into industry 5.0. As suggested by the European Union [3], progressing from industry 4.0, the new concept aims for sustainable, human-centric, and resilient industries that maximize strengths of both, technology and human, “by understanding where each excels” [4]. On the social impact level, industry 5.0 offers values such as job satisfaction, upskilling and reskilling, human agency, or improved customer experience [5]. By extension, automation today does not simply express the replacement of human workers but rather the enhancement or augmentation of human skills. Therefore, scholars have

noted that automation and augmentation exist at the same time and in the same space [6]. As noted by Raisch & Krakowski [6, p. 204], “we have to acknowledge that these human and machine agents do not simply coexist in separate worlds (working on separate tasks), but are interdependent (interacting on the same or closely related tasks)”.

Among the affected sectors, the professional services sector in particular questions the role of human workers where human interaction is often fundamental, and expertise is acquired over many years. Recently, advancements in AI have “brought professional services into the automation arena” [7, p. 124]. As such, increasingly smart technologies can take over certain tasks originally undertaken by workers or provide services directly to customers without the need of human intervention. For instance, robo-advisors have opened up online investment services through web- and app-interfaces without the need for human financial advisors, automating the process of investing. However, scholars have started noting the need for hybrid models of service delivery, including human and robo-advisors along the process to account for technological shortcomings [8].

As the technologies advance, individuals become empowered and turn to online services without human touch. With self-service technologies (SSTs) such as the robo-advisor, self-checkouts in supermarkets, and symptom checkers for medical diagnoses, customers have become co-producers of service delivery, often making additional service interactions from human to human redundant [9]. Thus, while SST becomes available and customers turn into co-creators, the effects on workers and the shift to such models have to be understood—an area that has been receiving growing attention [10], [11]. Although co-creation and co-production are two established concepts in the literature [12], value generation in service interactions is further transforming through SST adoption and increasing recognition of augmentation. As such, co-creation emphasizes “joint effort and collaboration between producer and the consumer”, underpinning “reciprocity and mutuality” in such interactions [12, p. 11]. However, the role of SST in that equation has not yet received much attention although “[t]he provision of service involves both employees and customers and can be provided by humans and/or machines” [2, p. 156].

While much research has been looking at service automation, self-service, and the changing nature of service encounters, few scholars have explored SST in the context of automation and augmentation, calling for a better understanding of service augmentation [7], [13], [14]. In particular an interdisciplinary lens is missing as research often looks at either technology adoption on the consumer side or at service aspects from the organizational side, missing out on understanding how the two are connected.

With the growing acknowledgment of an interdependence between automation and augmentation, a more holistic view on automation would allow us to understand automation not only from a “machine replacement” perspective but will open up a comprehensive “human augmentation” perspective that industry 5.0 calls for [3]. While we know that the process of introducing digital technology into organizations requires a holistic view on the micro-, meso-, and macro levels, e.g., [15], [16], we have yet to develop a holistic understanding of automation. A timely debate requires the acknowledgment of a significant lack of skills needed to advance into industry 5.0 [17]. Further challenges are represented by staff shortages across service industries where hybrid service provision and the mobilization of individuals on the consumer side is crucial in order to even sustain those services – especially in sectors such as finance, healthcare, education, or social services.

Therefore, with this paper we aim to bridge the literature on automation, augmentation and SST to understand their interdependencies and their mutual impact on service users and service workers. Presented as varying archetypes by De Keyser et al. [10], we zoom in on the role of SST for augmented service encounters. As “[f]irms should design human-machine integrated service strategies [...]” [2, p. 167], this paper aims to contribute to the further development of human-machine services for competitive edge, but, more so, for worker wellbeing and quality services. We do so by answering the following RQs:

- RQ1: What do we know about automation, augmentation and SST and how SST affects service workers?
- RQ2: How do automation, augmentation, and SST interact and what are emerging themes for future research?

II. METHOD

A. RESEARCH AIM

The aim of this paper is to provide a holistic understanding of the effects of SST on automation and augmentation in service industries as customers become increasingly engaged and informed, challenging the status quo of professionals across sectors. Though each of the topics alone have been studied in depth in their respective disciplines, what is currently missing is a contextualized approach that combines different viewpoints and provides a connected and integrative synthesis of the literature. In particular, as we see a significant growth in digital SST adoption (through AI and robotic applications specifically) and a rising recognition of augmentation, pinning the status quo of the debates helps to provide strategies moving forward. Therefore, we choose an integrative literature review, to draw on multi-disciplinary research in order to examine the role and interconnectedness of automation,

augmentation, and SST as they relate to knowledge workers. As such, we seek to consolidate and synthesize current research into an extended framework for service automation to guide further research, practice, and policy.

We select the integrative review in particular, as we believe that the topic “would benefit from a holistic conceptualization and synthesis of the literature” [18, p. 410] and the integrative review is shown to be “a powerful tool for studying organizational phenomena” [19, p. 187]. With the emergent empowerment of customers through the means of automation and its growing effects on workers through augmentation, we choose the integrative review to review, critique, and synthesize representative literature, and to reconceptualize and extend our understanding of automation [18, p. 411].

In this paper we build onto the concepts established by Raisch & Krakowski [6] and Sampson [7], [20] and suggest that SST through customer automation can advance worker augmentation—grounded in furthering the concept of industry 5.0. As the literature on these thematic areas remains dispersed, we provide an overview of these areas and how those can be consolidated. The goal of our selection process, as described below, was therefore not to be exhaustive but rather to engage more deeply with widely discussed and recent research to inform future research and theory development.

B. LITERATURE SELECTION

To select relevant literature for the review, a title, abstract, and keyword search was conducted using the Scopus database, considered one of the largest databases. For that purpose, a total of eight searches was undertaken using the search terms *automat**, *augment**, and *self-servi** each with AND “service” AND “digital” as well as the five search terms altogether, *automat* AND augment**, and in combination with *self-servi** and all three search terms together. Further, each search was narrowed down by focusing on English journal and review articles in three subject areas; (1) the social-sciences to understand the sociotechnical aspects of human-machine interaction, (2) business, to explore the management of technology adoption in organizations, and (3) economics, as much of the automation literature originates from the economist’s perspective [21], [22]. A preview of the automation literature reveals some often-cited works driving the debate. Thus, further narrowing down the literature and focusing the debate, highly cited articles were selected for review [23], [24], selecting the 10 most-cited articles for each search as well as the 10 most-cited articles for 2024 with respect to the topical dynamic and pace. In addition, the 10 most recent articles were selected to include the most recent developments and discussions in the field regardless of citation count which may not suffice as a standalone selection criterium.

Combining all search results led to a collection of 189 articles from which 59 duplicates were removed. From 130

papers another 71 were excluded that were, upon first inspection, not addressing the sociotechnical effects of automation, augmentation or self-service such as papers with an engineering perspective. 59 papers were screened further, resulting in the exclusion of 18 additional papers as their research focus did not fit the research scope and question. This finally resulted in 41 papers for in-depth review. The results from this process can be found in Table I.

TABLE I
SEARCH TERMS AND NUMBER OF LITERATURE RESULTS

Search terms	Total results	10 most highly cited	10 most highly cited in 2024	10 most recent
<i>augment*</i>	337	10	10	10
<i>AND service</i>				
<i>AND digital</i>				
<i>automat* AND service AND digital</i>	1113	10	10	10
<i>self-serv*</i>	105	10	10	10
<i>AND service</i>				
<i>AND digital</i>				
<i>self-serv* AND augment*</i>	25	10	2	10
<i>AND service</i>				
<i>AND digital</i>				
<i>self-serv* AND automat*</i>	152	10	10	10
<i>AND augment*</i>				
<i>automat* AND augment*</i>	1171	10	10	10
<i>AND self-serv*</i>				
<i>AND service AND digital</i>	6	6	1	6
<i>AND self-serv*</i>				
<i>AND service AND digital</i>	2	2	0	2
Total	2911	68	53	68
<u>SELECTION ROUND I</u>				
Highly cited + recent	189			
After duplicates removed	130			
<u>SELECTION ROUND II</u>				
After initial scoping	59			
<u>SELECTION ROUND III</u>				
Final sample after review	41			

As the Scopus database search shows, less than 3000 research and review articles can be found in the selected research disciplines, addressing some aspects of automation, augmentation, self-service, service, and/or digital. Most of those papers mention automation and augmentation together, followed by papers addressing automation, service, and digital at once. As Figure 1 shows, papers addressing automation and augmentation across all disciplines and publication types have

FIGURE 1. Scopus results for documents per year on automat* AND augment*

significantly increased in the last 8 years. Most of these, a combined 52,7%, are in the Computer Sciences and Engineering fields, 3,8% in the Social Sciences and even less in the fields of Business and Economics. Although SST has seen a similar but less significant increase since the 2000's (TITLE-ABS-KEY search on self-serv* technology), by contrast, SST has been addressed second most commonly in the business literature (22,2%), with the Computer Sciences (22,4%) ranking first. With our selection criteria, the topics that thus far have been least addressed in combination are self-service with augmentation and automation—even less so in the context of digital and service. For reference, there are almost 85.000 entries in Scopus on automation (with the same selection criteria), and 910.000 research and review articles across all disciplines—highlighting a gap in the literature looking at the connection of automation, augmentation, and self-service. The section below will detail the characteristics of the final sample and the procedure for data analysis.

C. ANALYSIS

Table II shows the final sample included for analysis. Selected papers provide a representative sample of the topic from the last two decades, ranging from 2005 to 2024. The sample consists of a combination of theoretical and empirical papers with 25 empirical papers, 4 systematic literature reviews, and 12 theoretical/conceptual papers. The sample covers various research disciplines including studies in management and organization, marketing and consumer behavior, information systems and technology, social sciences and public policy. Furthermore, there are sector-specific publications from healthcare, hospitality and tourism, public services, social services, retirement services, aviation, retail, finance, and professional services at large. While SST can refer to various types of technologies, most papers specify a type of technology with self-serving functions. The technologies studied range from information communication technologies (ICTs) and digital technologies at large, to self-service kiosks, voice assistants, robots, platforms, and AI in particular. The countries where empirical studies were set include a wide range from Northern European countries to Asia, South

Africa, South and North America, resulting in a mix of developed and developing countries.

As part of the analysis of papers, each paper was reviewed in-depth to explore how they approach automation, augmentation and/or SST individually and in connection. First, with respect to RQ1, this scoping process resulted in an overview of main topics around automation that the literature has commonly addressed: (1) the role of technologies for improving and changing work, job, and labor; (2) the relevance of human workers for specific areas; (3) the common resistance of workers to adopt to technologies due to a feeling of being replaced; (4) the changing and evolving relationships within and outside of organizations; and, finally, (5) the emergence of augmentation alongside automation. Secondly, with respect to RQ2, we reviewed and synthesized the literature further, focusing on emerging themes across automation, augmentation, and SST, building onto the first step. Through this structured process—collecting statements from the literature and forming groups—five themes emerged. As presented in Table III, some topics are commonly addressed in the literature across automation, augmentation, and SST. Those themes respectively move beyond those topics that are researched in each paper individually. As such, the resulting five themes highlight the interconnectedness of self-service, automation, and augmentation. These themes were further described and discussed. Furthermore, from the synthesis of the literature the conceptual model by Sampson [7], [20] was reviewed and adapted, discussing the role of SST in the presence of automation and augmentation [6] in services. To conclude, topics for further research were elaborated, based on the literature and emerging themes.

TABLE II
OVERVIEW OF SELECTED LITERATURE

Author	Journal	Year	Method a/Type	Tech- nology ^b	Sector ^c	Coun- try
[25]	Techno- vation	2024	Qual	VA	N/A	BR
[7]	J Serv Res	2021	Quan	AI	Profe- ssional	US
[6]	Acad Manage Rev	2021	Conc/ The	AI	N/A	N/A
[2]	J Serv Res	2018	Conc/ The	AI	N/A	N/A
[26]	Soc Cult Geogr	2024	Qual	SSK	Avia- tion	CN
[27]	Int J Soc Welf	2024	Quan	RPA	Social	SE
[28]	Gov Inf Q	2019	Conc/ The	Digital Public Services	Public	N/A
[29]	J Serv Manag	2018	Conc/ The	Virtual assistant & service robot	N/A	N/A
[30]	Psychol Mark	2024	Qual	Digital tech.	H&T	N/A
[31]	J Serv Res	2021	Conc/ The	AI	N/A	N/A

[32]	J Res Interact Mark	2021	Quan	AI	Ban-king	US (most-ly)	[55]	Int J Contemp Hosp Manag	2024	Conc/The	Auto-mated custo-mer assist-ant	N/A	N/A
[33]	Soc Policy Admin	2015	Qual	Web portal	Retire-ment,	NO	[56]	Asia Pac J Public Adm	2024	Quant	Disruptiv e audit tech	Audit-ing	ID
[34]	Soc Sci Med	2018	Qual	Mobile phones	Health-care	ZA	[57]	Gend Technol Dev	2024	Conc / The	Digital tech	HR	N/A
[1]	J Strateg Inf Syst	2015	Conc/The	Digitiza-tion, BDA	N/A	N/A	[58]	Nord Welf Res	2024	Qual	Digital Self-Service	Welf-are	NO
[35]	MIS Q Manag Inf Syst	2015	Conc/The	ICT	N/A	N/A	[59]	J Soc Welf	2023	Qual	Digital self-mgmt system	Public	SE
[36]	J Serv Manag	2019	Conc/The	ICT	H&T	N/A	[60]	Soc Policy Admin	2019	Qual	Digital post self-service	Welf-are	DK
[37]	Tour Manag Admin	2025	Quan	Robots	H&T	CN	<hr/> ^a Method/Type: Quant = quantitative methods; Qual = qualitative methods; Conc/The = conceptual/theoretical; SLR = systematic literature review; Mix = mixed methods. ^b Technology: VA = voice assistant; ICT = information communication technology; VR = voice response; RPA = robotic process automation; SSK = self-service kiosk; tech = technology; BDA = big data analytics. ^c Sector: H&T = Hospitality & Tourism; HR = human resources.						
[38]	J Bus Res	2020	Quan	Platform	Health-care	N/A							
[39]	Int J Inf Manag	2021	SLR	AI	N/A	N/A							
[40]	J Mark	2005	Quan	Interactiv e VR tele- phone system & Internet-based system	Health-care	N/A							
[41]	Manuf Serv Oper Manag	2007	Quan	VR units, ATMs, and online banking	Fin-ance	US							
[42]	J Bus Res	2020	Quan	Chatbot	H&T	America							
[43]	J Serv Res	2021	Quan	Service robots	H&T, Insu-rance, Avia-tion	UK							
[44]	Tour Manag	2021	Quan	Service robots	H&T	Europe							
[45]	Electron Commer Res Appl	2021	Mix	Kiosk, Compu-ter, Mobile Device	Entertai-nment, Public Trans- port	N/A							
[46]	J Bus Ind Mark	2024	Conc/The	AI	N/A	N/A							
[47]	J Hosp Tour Technol	2024	SLR	Smart tech	H&T	N/A							
[48]	World Econ	2024	Quant	AI	N/A	Japan							
[49]	J Travel Res	2024	Quant	Service robots	H&T	World wide							
[8]	IEEE Trans Eng Manag	2024	SLR	Robo advisors	Fin-ance	N/A							
[50]	J Res Interact Mark	2024	Conc/The	AI	N/A	N/A							
[51]	J Serv Theory Pract	2024	SLR	AI	Custo-mer ser-vice	N/A							
[52]	Conver-gence	2024	Qual	SSK	Retail	Germa ny							
[53]	J Serv Mark	2024	Quant	Robot, auto-matic machine	H&T	US							
[54]	New Media Soc	2024	Qual	SSK	H&T	China							

III. RESULTS

A. STATUS QUO OF THE LITERATURE (RQ1)

The search for literature addressing automation, augmentation, and SST has resulted in a small number of publications from various disciplines but with a higher concentration in service research, information systems, business and management research. Surprisingly, literature addressing the three search terms at once appears to be rare. However, the review shows some topics commonly addressed that are: (1) how jobs are affected by the adoption of (digital) technologies, (2) the role of human touch and empathy in customer interactions, (3) the threat posed by technology adoption and resulting resistance by workers, (4) new and changing relationships within and across organizational boundaries as the service ecosystem adapts, (5) the emergence and growing attribution of augmentation.

This section begins with a brief explanatory introduction to the three terms—automation, augmentation, and SST—and how they interlink. Subsequently, we discuss and present current engagement of scholars with the topics of automation, augmentation and self-service, and how SST affects service professionals and the service encounter.

1) FROM AUTOMATION TO AUGMENTATION AND SST

At its core, automation refers to the introduction of technology, thereby shifting tasks traditionally done by humans to be machine operated. Today, the introduction of digital technology in organizations oftentimes leads to digital transformation, fundamentally changing how businesses operate and deliver value, requiring adapting entire ways of working [1]. Aside from operational changes, digitally savvy customers increasingly necessitate the development of new products and services. With vast information available online and freely accessible AI solutions, a range of services today

are thus gradually losing attractiveness, giving rise to digital self-serving applications without human touch. As a result, digital technology in services has significantly changed the delivery of services for both, employees and customers, shifting roles and responsibilities throughout [26], [52].

Although since the first industrial revolution, automation has mostly affected production industries and blue-collar workers, digital technology has exponentially affected knowledge-intensive and service-oriented sectors—not least since the Covid-19 pandemic. With more service encounters becoming automated and machine operated, however, scholars have noted the role of interpersonal elements and human touch [8]. AI technologies, in particular, further blur boundaries between human and machine, questioning the value added by each. As such, fostering a clearer division of labour, routine tasks may become machine-operated, while human workers may become essential touchpoints for customers. With the goal of enabling human-machine collaboration, rather than replacing human workers, machines become contributors or co-workers, whether in the digital or physical space. Alongside technological innovations from industry 1.0 to 4.0, we are now beginning to center our attention not on the technology but on the role of human workers. Although automation has advanced to impact physical and mental work equally, we have become progressively aware of augmentation where “humans collaborate closely with machines to perform a task” [6, p. 193].

Combined, automation and augmentation reflect approaches to technology adoption in organizations. In services in particular, however, technology often lies at the intersection of service user and service provider (or worker). The provision of timely, accessible and digital services therefore has resulted in a number of self-service solutions, automating various services. Yet, the replacement of human workers and full automation of such services often remains undesirable while augmentation currently misses clear strategies. In particular, many services continue to be built on trust, relationships (with workers), and receiving quality professional advice and care—aspects not always achievable with automated services—calling for augmentation. As such, recent developments and changes in service industries shed a new light on automation as we move towards increasingly smart (AI-driven) self-services, necessitating pathways for integrated human-machine service models and augmentation.

2) TECHNOLOGIES FOR JOB IMPROVEMENT

With the first introduction of machines into the workplace, automation has been understood as a way to replace human labor. Then scholars have pointed to the significance of human beings in the workplace; a significant contribution in recent days is made by Sampson [7] who encourages to focus on job improvement rather than displacement. He further suggests that automation affects different tasks in different ways. Accordingly, first, tasks can be augmented by automation and

remain with workers. Second, some tasks are deskilled by automation resulting in a transfer to lower cost workers. And third, tasks are moved to customers via SST, leading to a reduction or elimination of worker interaction. Despite various ways to automate, McLeay et al. [43] however calls for caution, finding how worker replacement can have ethical and societal implications for service providers [43].

Other means to automate, in parts aligning with Sampson, are presented, by Loebbecke & Picot [1] who distinguish five mechanisms where digitization and big data analytics affect labor. Through self-service, they argue, labor within physical processes can be substituted. High-level decision making on the other hand can be machine supported, substituting only some share of the work. In other mechanisms Loebbecke & Picot [1] share a pessimism for the relevance of human labor. Accordingly, knowledge work will be eliminated by data scientists and algorithms, and through new products and services, “physical forerunners” too will be replaced. As one last mechanism, more professional jobs will be split into smaller chunks of work overtaken by a growing mass of amateurs.

Though some scholars believe in an increasing substitution of experts, they also suggest focusing on skills harder to automate, such as intellectual expertise, compassion, teamwork, ethical judgement, or cultural understanding. As described by Brady & Lin [26, p. 534], automation through self-service should be seen as transformation and “a synthesis and redistribution of roles” rather than an elimination of worker’s labor. In a similar way, Pentzold & Bischof call SST a “catalyst for restructuring labor” [61, p. 960]. Yet another suggestion for redirecting worker’s focus, as suggested by Breit & Salomon [33], may be towards increasingly complex work – a suggestion seemingly unmatched with Loebbecke & Picot [1]. Similarly, Altrock et al. [8] look at the interaction of robo-advisors, automated investment management tools, with human financial advisors, suggesting that dependent on technological ability, human advisors need to adapt their skills. As such, a less advanced robo-advisor requires human-machine collaboration (or augmentation), whereas a more advanced robo-advisor requires human advisors to reskill and redirect into other areas [8].

3) VALUING THE EMPATHETIC SPACE

While different strategies exist as to what happens to workers when automation is being introduced, scholars show a general tendency towards a focus on human-centered tasks. Yousofi et al. [30] empirically research digital technology adoption in the hotel industry, finding that when guests use digital technologies (i.e., SST), hotel professionals can enhance their competence as tasks become more efficient and cost-effective. While guests experience autonomy, employees are then enabled to allocate time to more qualitative and human-centric tasks and make client interactions more meaningful. Rather than eliminating interactive tasks [7] or moving to technology related functions [1], the shift is then towards more meaningful

client interactions. Similarly, Lindgren et al. [28] note how “automation can lead to more interesting work”. As such, workers not only become bystanders but rather take on an engaging or a supportive role next to the technology. As described also by Brady & Lin [26] who explore the aviation industry, workers provide technical assistance and handle problems, thereby resembling the “empathetic space” to the technical interface. This may result partially in a reduction of interaction but more so in an expansion of their role into more meaningful interactions [7].

Despite the potential for automation technologies, SST in particular, to enhance communication and interaction among workers and consumers, they also risk affecting interpersonal relationships negatively. For instance, technologies may lead to a dehumanization of the service experience as users opt for technological solutions and workers are being replaced [36]. Furthermore, looking at the financial sector, Manser Payne et al. [32] add reduced opportunities for interpersonal communication and negative effects on relationships marketing as potential outcomes of automation. Furthermore, in public and welfare services automation and the use of self-service applications can mean significant shortcomings for disadvantaged and vulnerable citizens [58], [60]. Here, automation may lead to dehumanization and depersonalization that generates barriers for users, restricting access to services they need [58], [59], [60].

4) MITIGATING THE AUTOMATION THREAT

In the long history of automation, the fear of replacement has been a significant concern, requiring efforts today to still think of its effect on individuals. Pan et al. [37] show what happens if outcomes of automation are neglected. With a focus on automation that disregards impact on employees, those may not only be de facto at risk to be replaced, as a possible outcome [7], but will even feel threatened, resulting in negative outcomes. Pan et al. [37] empirically explore robot adoption in the hotel industry. Yet, despite the potential benefits to guests and employees, they find that excessive organizational investments and high customer satisfaction can increase feelings of being threatened. This, as suggested by Pan et al. [37], calls for continuous recognition from the company and customers so that employees do not fear replacement – as organizations intent to retain workers.

Across sectors the changes affecting workers will be quite diverse. As shown in the Indonesian public sector, workers certainly recognize the relevance for self-service solutions, although they believe their expertise gap to be very high [56]. In order to integrate solutions with workers thus requires understanding the differences and preparing workers to adapt. For instance, Persson et al. show how HR practices shift from street-level to screen-level, requiring masculine-coded practices (rational, instrumental) that were originally female-coded practices (nurturing, supportive) [57]. And while repetitive tasks are the ones who should be first to be modeled [36], adoption of anthropomorphic AI and service robots

become increasingly accepted by users, challenging the relevance of workers and possibly maintaining the threat if not managed [42], [43], [44], [47], [49], [51], [53].

5) MANAGING NEW RELATIONSHIPS

With the balancing of human workers and machines in service interactions, clarifying responsibilities is at the forefront of enabling automation. Next to ambivalent outcomes of automation for workers, the same goes for service users at the other end of the co-creating value chain [45], [46] [43]. Lindgren et al. [28] support but also criticize the use of automated systems in their study of public services. As they argue, algorithmic decision-making enforces an asymmetrical power relationship. Although in the hotel industry guests can feel increasing autonomy, “public services range from having a limited influence on a citizen's life to being of great importance to a citizen's economic situation and well-being” [28]. As also Germundsson & Stranz [27] caution, caseworkers in social services “might become less inclined to exercise their professional discretion,” once automation has been introduced. Thus, the automation of such services, and the different characteristics and unique qualities of human and technology-driven service provision should be carefully explored as the lines become blurred [28], [58], [60]. For instance, as noted above, some tasks such as compassion or ethical judgement [1] may be more human-centric than others and should thus remain with human workers [30]. However, contrasting an increase in asymmetric power and disadvantaging service users, Buhalis et al. [36] and Leite et al. [25] suggest that technologies also increase inclusiveness and accessibility to otherwise disadvantaged individuals such as the elderly and people with special needs who, for instance, may be physically restricted and might welcome digital applications.

As traditional organizations can be slow to adopt, emerging organizations play an increasingly important role catering directly to consumers in need of accessible solutions. For instance, in the healthcare sector new market segments are developing, offering their solutions directly to consumers. As healthcare access can be difficult in some countries, emerging organizations provide self-care, preventive telemedicine, and disease prediction applications [38]. This allows patients to become more empowered and self-reliant without the need to go to a doctor. As Watkins et al. [34] highlight, in emerging countries certain gaps must be filled to augment healthcare. Thus, health workers and patients in South Africa develop their own digital communication tools, manage chronic diseases digitally, and access health information using the internet [34]. This shift, as Hermes et al. [38] argue, is moving an entire industry from linear two-sided markets to “complex interacting multi-sided markets mediated by platforms with super-modular/super-additive value creation” as SST becomes more than a “standalone feature” [41]. While patients, or individuals, had to go to a hospital or primary care provider, these roles are now being replaced and supplemented by

technology providers of digital health applications, as suggested by Loebbecke & Picot [1]. This application of technology is what Barrett et al. [35] describe as central for “the formation and functioning of service ecosystems” as resources are “combined and exchanged in new ways that create value for those actors engaged in the exchange”. Underpinning this shift in actors, Breit & Salomon [33] point to a gradual embeddedness of complex relations among citizens, frontline workers and digital infrastructures, moving away from the dyadic relationship. Similarly, Bolton et al. [29] describe an integration of the digital, physical and social realms, pushing organizations to acquire partnerships, network alliances, and finding mechanisms for aligning goals across actors.

6) ASSESSING AUGMENTATION

As automation is still increasingly adopted, the shift in service interactions between human workers, customers, and technology intensifies—in particular with the introduction of AI. The majority of scholars are pointing to augment rather than replace [46], [47], [48], [55], as exemplified also by Pentzold & Bischof [61] in what they title “imperfect automation”. In 2018, Huang & Rust [2] define five stages of AI affecting jobs. While stages one to five suggest replacement of jobs with mechanical, analytical, intuitive and empathetic direction, the last stage depicts replacement or, more importantly, “complete integration with human workers”. Huang & Rust [2] name three factors for firms to consider automation with AI. Namely, the nature of the task, the nature of the service, and the strategic emphasis of the firm. A strategic focus is also brought up by Borges et al. [39] who suggest adjusting the AI–human equation “in alignment with business needs and digital strategies”. As a result, automation could be enabled that would generate competitive advantage for firms. Three years later Huang & Rust [31] present a continuation of their work, shifting increasingly towards the use of the word augmentation instead of replacement. Accordingly, different types of AI are existent with varying effects on human workers: mechanical AI, thinking AI, and feeling AI. As such, mechanical AI replaces human workers such as through SST, aligning on this aspect with Sampson [7] and Loebbecke & Picot [1]. Thinking tasks however “should” and feeling tasks “may” be performed by both, human and AI.

The growing tendency towards augmentation has since evolved into somewhat of a necessity. As put by Raisch & Krakowski [6], “augmentation cannot be neatly separated from automation”. As we move “away from the question of what defines humans and distinguishes them from smart machines and towards querying how people and technology come together” [61], management perspectives have progressed. Put forward by Raisch & Krakowski’s [6] analysis, automation and augmentation are “interdependent across time and space”. Thus, through a coevolutionary process, humans and machines learn from one another, augmentation facilitates automation, and automation may

enable augmentation. The determining factor for each application however is, as already defined by Huang & Rust [2], the nature of the task.

In summation, automation, augmentation and SST are topics of vast interest by scholars from various fields and industries. Though some technologies replace human workers, scholars are increasingly pointing towards the redefining of roles or the improvement of labor. While some sectors are built significantly on human interaction such as public services or the hospitality and tourism industry, human workers remain present in many ways. As some tasks may be automated, human workers become the interface between technology and service user. As SST offers accessible service to users, service workers adapt, either moving towards technology-related tasks, empathetic tasks, or more complex cases. As AI continues to develop and digital service becomes increasingly available across markets, organizations that automate will have to strategize along the ways of automation and augmentation, keeping the human in the loop. Though this chapter has provided some topical overview, themes emerge across the topics of automation, augmentation, and SST that the following chapter will address.

B. EMERGING THEMES FROM THE LITERATURE (RQ2)

From an in-depth review and synthesis of the literature, five research themes evolve around the topics of automation, augmentation, and SST. While the previous section has focused on providing a general overview of automation, augmentation, and SST, the objective of answering the second RQ is to explore how the three are connected. In carefully reviewing the literature, we have found five emerging themes that provide an important interdisciplinary foundation for further research. Those are: (1) social (a)symmetries, (2) competing intelligences, (3) redistributed responsibilities and new skills, (4) merging spaces and new ecosystems, and (5) governance and ethics. Each theme described below highlights a fundamental aspect for enabling automation and augmentation through SST in service contexts. Table III provides an overview of how emerging themes were systematically derived from the literature with respective references.

1) SOCIAL (A)SYMMETRIES

With the increasing adoption of SST, accessibility of services changes. However, SST adoption has two sides to this. On one hand, SST allows to democratize service and enable access to information and communication tools as can be seen in developing countries where, for instance, healthcare access is an issue [34]. SST allows to provide information and enhance services where those can otherwise not be easily accessed. On the other hand, SST does not represent a benefit to all, in particular, to disadvantaged groups. Few examples from developed countries show significant issues in providing self-service options and automating services. For instance, welfare

services push the digital divide where disadvantaged or vulnerable citizens are becoming even more disadvantaged by these new services [58], [60]. Public and welfare services, as a result, become increasingly dehumanized, shifting responsibility from workers to individuals [59]. Thus, SST leads to mounting asymmetries as not all consumers have access or abilities to use digitalized services without the help of workers [27], [28]. Yet, often times, automation supersedes augmentation, resulting in job replacement or significant role changes. As a result, those unwilling or unable to adapt will be affected to leave their job.

TABLE III
OVERVIEW OF EMERGING THEMES

Source	Research Theme
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Vulnerable citizens suffer with SST [58] • Consumer characteristics can affect the digital service experience [30] • SST makes disadvantaged citizens even more disadvantaged [60] • Automation creates asymmetric worker-client relationships [59] • Technologies increase inclusiveness and accessibility to otherwise disadvantaged individuals [25], [36] • Algorithmic decision-making enforces an asymmetrical power relationship [28] • SST increases availability of services, speed, and access to information at any time [33], [34] • Organizations must ensure that clients are not asymmetrically affected [27] • Digitization and big data analytics may hit knowledge-based workers as hard and potentially faster than non-knowledge workers [1] • AI complements the work of teleworkers (RI) [48] • AI improves human work, intelligence automation (AI), by contrast, enhances human intelligence towards new things [46] • AI needs to provide personalized conversation and personal touch [51] • Different types of AI have varying effects on human workers: mechanical AI, thinking AI, and feeling AI [31] • Digitization and big data analytics complement and replace labor differentially across industry sectors and work processes [1] • Abilities of human and technology need to be matched [8] • Consumers require role clarity, motivation, and ability for SST use [40] • With SST users become disciplined customers [54] • Customers become partial employees; but co-creation also entails co-destruction [45] • Users become empowered and self-reliant [38] • Workers are shifting tasks to help enable users' digital literacy [60] • AI requires human oversight and accountability [62] • Services retain worker involvement for formal decisions [28] 	<p><i>Social (a)symmetries</i></p> <p><i>Competing intelligences</i></p> <p><i>Redistributed responsibilities and new skills</i></p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Anthropomorphism increases acceptance of automation technologies [44], [53] • Imperfect automation requires new skills from employees and customers [52] • Automation requires a redistribution of roles [26] • Self-service reinforces responsabilisation of users [59] • SST moves tasks to customers, reducing or eliminating worker interaction and interpersonal communication [7], [32] • Knowledge work will shift to data scientists and algorithms [1] • Humans and machines learn from one another [6] • Employees move to human-centric tasks and make client interactions more meaningful [30] • Automation represents a masculine transformation away from female coded practices as nurturer and supporter [57] • Automation may result in a more engaging or a supportive role of workers [28] • Automation through SST is a synthesis and redistribution of roles [26] • SST frees up human resources for more complex tasks [33] • Citizens, frontline workers and digital infrastructures become gradually embedded [33] • Digital, physical and social realms merge [29] • Internet-based technologies facilitate new channels for communication [28] • Value creation evolves as resources are exchanged and redistributed among actors in new ways [35] • With designers and providers of technology a new group of actors is introduced [28] • Markets become complex multi-sided platforms with new ways of value creation [38] • Emerging organizations embrace significantly different value propositions than traditional organizations [38] • Interaction is gradually taken on by third parties [38] • New economies evolve as distributed networks, interacting with customers over platforms [36] • Service innovation in one dimension can result in changes in other dimensions within and across organizational boundaries [35] • Co-creation becomes difficult as solutions are disconnected [29] • Worker replacement has ethical and societal consequences [43] • Confidentiality and ethics are relevant factors for effectiveness of digital service [30] • Self-service is not service, service requires personalization, expertise, experience, and empathy [55] • Self-service enforces depersonalization and dehumanization [36], [59] • Responsible service automation is needed to avoid bias [50] • Automation can be defined by the nature of the task, nature of the service, and strategic emphasis of the firm [2] • AI-human integration needs to happen in alignment with business needs and digital strategies [39] 	<p><i>Merging spaces and new ecosystems</i></p> <p><i>Governance and ethics</i></p>

- Organizations need to manage automation so that employees do not feel threatened [37]
- Overemphasizing augmentation or automation may enforce negative organizational or societal outcomes [6]

2) COMPETING INTELLIGENCES

Without a doubt, AI is driving the opportunities for automation, especially in knowledge intensive work significantly [2]. This is leading to automation impacts on jobs and sectors previously presumed to be unaffected by automation. Many scholars looking at AI predict a high replacement of workers due to its abilities as it becomes able to “think” and “feel” [2], [31]. The increasing ability of technology stresses the need to understand the complexities of tasks and the requirements for human touch to model human-machine interaction at the intersection of automation and augmentation [6]. SST refers to various types of technology from chatbots, to robots, self-service kiosks, and often, simply to AI. Any technology will be able to integrate less and more complex algorithms and various types of AI. This will range from simple automation, providing information via chatbot to complex automation, offering individualized recommendations through an anthropomorphic robot. As our technologies become increasingly advanced, it is fundamentally important to explore the potential and risks of AI and the actual and realistic needs of human and technology components in service interactions.

3) REDISTRIBUTED RESPONSIBILITIES AND NEW SKILLS

One of the major themes across automation, augmentation, and SST literature is the changing roles and responsibilities. And while Roberts and Maier argue that self-service is, in fact, not service at all [55], Pentzold and Bischof instead argue for imperfect automation [61], where SST restructures labor. Automation then rather requires rethinking responsibilities and the role of customers, workers, and SST[8], [61] where with hybrid and multichannel service models, all three components seem to be able to come together [41], [55]. With SST consumers become co-producers of value creation or “working customers” [54], making customers into partial employees [45] that organizations are required to manage [58]. Workers, on the other hand, will either shift to manage customer adoption of digital services [57], [60] or work on more complex and personalized services, e.g., [8], [26]. The role of the third component, the SST, will depend on customer needs, how anthropomorphic the interaction can be, and what human touchpoints will have to remain, e.g., [43], [53], [55].

4) MERGING SPACES AND NEW ECOSYSTEMS

While service interaction can be viewed from various angles, the adoption of SST and increasing automation merges the physical with the digital and the social world [29], [33]. This shifts a traditional service encounter into a multilevel

relationship that surpasses those boundaries. As we move towards new models of service delivery where service can be enacted virtually and digitally, we augment the human interaction from the physical space and extend the service experience by technological means. Value-creation becomes enacted across dimensions and actors in new ways [35]. This challenges markets and stakeholders as platforms become multi-sided, involving actors within and outside organizational boundaries such as the working customer [38], [54].

5) GOVERNANCE AND ETHICS

As the increasing adoption of SST redefines the responsibilities and interactions of actors across service delivery, overarching frameworks are evolving gradually. For instance, as scholars have noted, automation should be explored on a task level instead of a job level [2], [7]. Thus, automation should not just be a solution for improving efficiency. Automation instead should be considered carefully with augmentation in order to establish human and machine abilities and where and how they interact [6], [44], [47]. Service requires personalization, expertise, experience, and empathy [55], thus questioning the meaning of service and the interaction of actors in new and evolving models. As technology becomes an “operant resource” [35], able to replace human workers, it may enter the space of being a responsible actor; a responsible actor that risks offering dehumanized practices, enacting preexisting bias [36], [59]. This requires practices for responsible service automation [50], managing automation without threatening employees [37], and considering carefully ethical as well as societal consequences [43].

IV. DISCUSSION

A. CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

The review and synthesis of the literature provides a more detailed understanding of the connection between SST, automation, and augmentation that previous literature has only been beginning to address across disciplines. Automation in the 21st century however, approaching the concept of the 5th industrial revolution [3] driven by increasingly intelligent technologies, has long surpassed the meaning of human replacement and full automation. In particular in the service context, automation is not an isolated or straightforward phenomenon. To automate means to decide what can be done by a machine better (more efficiently) than a human, to know where human ability is fundamental (empathetic space), and to clearly define when the two meet and human ability is being augmented instead [6]. To automate also means to understand the involvement of actors and the shifting responsibilities. Automation affects organizations from within – workers, processes, tasks, technologies – and across organizational boundaries – i.e. consumers, competitors, governments,

legislators, policies, etc., e.g., [29], [36], [63]. To speak of automation is to speak of human beings and how technologies will be instrumental in supporting and augmenting work in order to service individuals across the globe.

Traditional service theory understands the service encounter as dyadic relationship of service provider and service user. However, conceptualizations have evolved. Bateson [64] introduced triadic models, adding organizations, followed by Parasuraman & Grewal [65] (first presented in Parasuraman [66]) enhancing the triangle to a pyramid model, reflecting the role of technology as a fourth point [67]. Reflected in connectedness, the three actors, technology, customer, and worker somewhat co-exist and co-work simultaneously for the benefit of value co-creation in service interactions [11]. In our understanding of automation employees are replaced by machines and work shifts to technology. With SST however, work shifts to consumers (through technology) while the empathetic space remains relevant for many service interactions. As such, work becomes augmented, and workers may retain agency along with reduced workloads and improved wellbeing. Yet, SST does not merely automate as consumers co-create or rather create the service entirely on their own (such as in self-checkout kiosks at the supermarket). SST evolves into what is rather a multisided platform for hybrid service delivery where consumers access a service independently but, simultaneously, workers retain access to that service and the data it creates. As stated by Xue et al., “[s]elf-service systems are more than just a standalone feature” [41, p. 538]. If and when required, service encounters are then enabled within the platform (e.g., in a chat), across the platform (e.g., enabling service encounters virtually through videochat), or outside of the platform (e.g., when an in-person interaction is mandated or required after interacting with it). For instance, in the latter case, imagine a digital healthcare application that tracks the patients’ health data for weeks, noticing an anomaly. The application will trigger an alert for the patient and/or healthcare professional, suggesting an in-person visit. As such, the SST not simply automates but augments by connecting service user and service provider if and when needed while retaining benefit for customers through (what is more) automation and for workers through (what is more) augmentation.

In a framework by Sampson [7] (first presented in [20]), three modes are presented, depicting the relationships between system, professional (worker), and customer. Here, Mode 1 supports or augments the job as professionals use the system. In Mode 2, professional’s work is being downskilled, and paraprofessionals take on the role of using the system and interacting with customers. In Mode 3, professional’s job is being automated as customers begin to interact with the system or SST. Yet, as research has shown and service models evolve, even the use of SST involves workers in some way. This may be, for instance, as the “empathetic space” to the technical interface [26] or when it becomes necessary of users

to get in touch with human workers as they reach the limits of SST and require, for instance, more meaningful interactions [30]. In that sense, however, interactions transcend physical, digital, and social space. Depending on the sector or tasks in question, human interaction can be happening through the interface, such as in telemedicine, or in-person, such as next to the self-service kiosk.

FIGURE 2. Automation—Augmentation Entanglement in Services, Extended from Sampson [6], [18]

Based on the here presented discussion, it seems therefore sensible to extend Sampson’s model and suggest Mode 4, see Figure 2, where SST automates and augments professionals’ job and, as required, the technology provides an interface not just for the customer but also for the worker side in order to enable interaction within and across spaces. The self-service aspect remains but opens up into enhancing its value proposition and service provision by enabling, for instance, worker interaction or supervision. This idea aligns with the two prominent ideas that automation and augmentation coevolve, and that SST is here to stay – not only for professional but for services in general. Instead of denying self-service to be service [55] and calling automation imperfect [61], we encourage the idea of SST catalyzing the restructuring of labor, making customers co-producers [32], [45], [46], and pushing the need for hybrid services [8], [41], [55], and entangling augmentation in service work [6], [34], [46], [48]. Although Sampson focuses on professional services, the literature shows similar effects for service sectors at large, suggesting that Mode 4 could also be more generally applied to services where service worker and customer interact – though the relevance of professional expertise and knowledge would need further exploration as also the theme on competing intelligences suggests. We discuss theoretical and practical implications further below. Before that, in order to establish such models successfully and sustainably, a better understanding of the five themes that emerged from the literature is still required; areas for future research are therefore discussed below.

B. TOWARDS A RESEARCH AGENDA

As Mode 4 evolves in practice, more research is needed to understand the role of SST at the intersection of automation and augmentation in service work. In particular, the five emerging themes, see Table III, in the literature require further exploration: (1) social (a)symmetries, (2) competing intelligences, (3) redistributed responsibilities and new skills, (4) merging spaces and new ecosystems, and (5) governance and ethics. Resulting from the review and discussion presented above, Table IV provides an overview of future research areas

and questions. In sum, the research areas and questions provide a better understanding of the adoption of SST, towards the facilitation of automation and augmentation.

TABLE IV
OVERVIEW OF FUTURE RESEARCH AGENDA

Theme	Research area	Example questions
(1)	a) Advantages and disadvantages across contexts, countries, services	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How does SST adoption differ across service sectors? • What is the role of accessibility across services / contexts / countries?
	b) Political and regulatory dimensions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What services require more augmentation than automation?
(2)	c) Responsibility and accountability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How do responsibility and accountability shift with AI entering services / SST?
	d) Employee motivation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How are employees and employee motivation affected by automation with SST?
	e) Variations in AI	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How are different types of service work affected by AI?
	f) Types of service work	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How do roles of service workers change in light of AI?
(3)	g) Associated risks	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What are the risks associated with shifting roles and responsibilities (i.e., customers gaining access and independence without oversight)?
	h) Education and literacy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How do education and digital literacy affect automation and augmentation efforts?
	i) Roles of stakeholders	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What is the role of e.g., organizations, workers, and customers when automating and augmenting?
(4)	j) Platform and interface design	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How do boundaries merge with digital SST and how does it affect service delivery? • What is the role of startup and traditional organizations and how do they affect one another?
(5)	k) Moral and ethical dimensions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What are moral and ethical obligations of organizations?
	l) Management and leadership	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How can management and leadership support automation and augmentation in organizations?

For instance, although the role of SST for different groups has been researched, future research should continue to look at the advantages and disadvantages of SST across contexts, countries, services, and so forth. While research suggests a benefit of SST in particular in low-income countries, it will be important to expand on the development and adoption of SST in those countries. However, this also demands to engage further with political and regulatory dimensions as well as access to such solutions and what is required to continue enabling these solutions that are so much required. Across services, SST provides many opportunities to increase access to, e.g., healthcare or financial services that consumers would

otherwise not have, underlining the importance of continuing developments and research in this field.

Furthermore, this also implies the need for understanding the redistribution of responsibilities. While it may be extremely useful in some cases to allow SST access, certain risks can be associated when consumers are gaining access to information and functionalities that they do not know how to interpret or how to act upon. Education on both sides, consumers as well as workers, who will be affected by SST adoption will be a priority. Where the responsibility lies however and how to provide such education and information might be unclear, representing another important topic. This research stream also includes understanding the role of various stakeholders such as service users, service providers such as organizations (incumbent and emerging) and their workers, governments, and policy makers.

As digital, physical, and social spaces merge, many obstacles relating to responsibility, regulation, and more become relevant. Future research should explore how service will be working across the three dimensions involving and engaging service users and providers through SST and what will be required of interfaces, technologically and organizationally. Aside from the public, organizations will also be required to provide training and education to employees affected by such changes to ensure literacy and upkeep employee motivation as responsibilities at work shift. This refers in particular to instances where AI will be incorporated, and tasks will become increasingly automated and independent of human involvement. More research is required to understand variations in AI and how it interferes with various types of service and professional work, exploring types of service work, knowledge workers, service professionals, and so forth. This includes further empirical investigation based on Huang & Rust [31].

More research will also be needed to establish the role of organizations, management, and leadership as automation and augmentation are being integrated. This will in particular be a relevant topic to be explored across service sectors to understand variations and build appropriate models accordingly.

C. THEORETICAL IMPLICATIONS

In this paper the most highly cited and most recent publications on automation, augmentation, and SST were reviewed to explore the relevance and connectedness of these topics across service sectors. This investigation was motivated by and built on research by Sampson [7], [20] and Raisch & Krakowski [6] who explore the relevance of and connection between automation and augmented work. In this review we contribute to the debate by showing the entanglement of automation, augmentation, and SST. With individuals across the globe increasingly seeking to self-serve for finances, healthcare, tourism, and more, and workers steadily being overworked, we require a review of old service models. Current and future service models thus will be required to

make customer and worker meet in the middle, providing benefits of efficiency and service quality to both. Over the years, automation and augmentation have coevolved into a mounting focus on augmentation and, thus, the relevance of the human-in-the-loop. As we have shown, previous scholars have explored various technology applications at the intersection of employees and customers as well as within and across organizational boundaries. Nonetheless, automation depends on the nature of the task and a firm's strategy. As such, automation may be more appropriate for some tasks while augmentation will be appropriate for other, more human-centered tasks.

Although there is a large number of articles on automation and self-service that go back to the first industrial revolution in the 18th century and, later on, automated teller machines (ATMs) in the 1960s, business and management scholars have not yet expanded on the relationship of automation, augmentation, and SST per se. What they did argue for, for example, is imperfect automation [61] and the lack of service in SST [55]. Notably, there is various literature on digitalization, the adoption of automation technologies, human-machine collaboration and so forth. However, two developments are colliding that require the here presented debate: the increasing possibilities with AI for users to self-serve and the growing acknowledgment of augmentation and worker wellbeing.

Building on Raisch & Krakowski [6], the literature suggests a growing relevance of what we call an *automation-augmentation entanglement* whereby automation (human replacement) and augmentation (human-machine collaboration) coevolve and do not exist without the other as we move beyond industry 4.0 and into AI-driven, human-centered service provision. This integrates the sociomaterial lens from Orlikowski and Scott, suggesting the entanglement of technology and work in organizations [68]. As such, they "preclude the possibility of seeing the social and material worlds as distinct" [68, p. 27]. Following Orlikowski, a view of entanglement thus does not simply center on human workers but provides guidance to organization scholars to "take seriously the recursive intertwining of humans and technology in practice" [69, p. 1437] to provide better outcomes for human workers. This lens has been proven to be relevant in the SST context as shown by Pentzold and Bischof [61]. Thus, scholars should continue to explore service automation holistically and entangled across levels in order to increase our understanding of the evolving relationship between employees, customers, and technology. SST provides many benefits as platform applications at the intersection of consumers and workers, and, taking the findings of this paper as starting point, future research across disciplines could support sensible and sustainable adoption in the future.

D. LIMITATIONS

Despite the contributions this paper provides, there are certain limitations that should be noted. The aim of this integrative

review was to explore automation, augmentation, and SST and their interconnectedness to understand how SST can contribute to customer automation and worker augmentation. We chose a limiting literature selection approach to focus only on most highly cited and most recent research due to the widespread and extensive literature on automation. This approach limits the findings to a small sample and might question how results might change with a broader literature selection. However, it should be noted, that the goal of this process was not to cover a broad range and cover every piece of scholarship but rather to understand the most significant evolving research themes. Despite the in-depth insights into the literature, we understand that the process itself limits itself to subjectivity and a difficulty for replicability. We therefore offer transparency and systematic approaches to limit those effects but unable to eliminate those effects completely. The literature sample provides diverse insights from empirical and theoretical papers across disciplines with diverse foci. This enables a broad understanding of the topic, however, risks oversimplification and generalization as we synthesize viewpoints and findings. In order to complement some of these shortcomings more research will be needed.

E. PRACTICAL IMPLICATIONS

Though theoretical in nature, this paper provides few insights for practitioners as well. We thus present an overview into different applications of SST in service and how it not only provides efficient and effective services to customers, but how it, simultaneously, provides augmentation potential to workers. As such, practitioners are encouraged, where possible, to consider SST in hybrid ways of service delivery where human service extends beyond technology in services that very commonly value human interaction. Based on the findings from the literature review, a few fundamental suggestions for consideration by managers and policy makers are the following:

- **Technologies for Job Improvement:** Understand possibilities of SST and investigate where and how to automate and augment in service interactions. In particular, with the adoption of AI and anthropomorphic applications (such as robots), organizations need to consider the impact on customers and workers simultaneously.
- **Valuing the Empathetic Space:** Explore where consumers require human touch. This is especially relevant for social or welfare services, or generally services that cater to a diverse group of individuals and disadvantaged individuals. Certain services with traditionally high human touch need to be cautious about automation.
- **Mitigating the Automation Threat:** Communicate to workers about automation and augmentation efforts and keep workers accountable and involved. Levelling up on automation and augmentation shifts responsibilities, accountability, and requires managers and policy

- makers to be aware of social and ethical consequences.
- **Managing New Relationships:** Explore emerging and possible relationships within service delivery and across organizational boundaries. As social, physical, and digital borders merge, organizations should be considerate of those effects and learn how to increase value from it.
 - **Assessing Augmentation:** Focus on augmenting instead of automating. Many service sector activities can be automated, but many others require to be augmented and maintain workers. This leads to a significant shift in roles and responsibilities and asks for exploring this transformation in value co-creation and, potentially, how to manage customers as partial employees.

As the literature review has shown, various services can be affected, requiring any type of service organization to consider augmentation. For instance, building onto the visual of Mode 4, a healthcare organization might introduce an app for patients to track medication or even to access therapeutic content. While providing accessible content to patients to be managed and accessed by the patient, healthcare professionals do not become redundant. Rather and specifically in such a high-risk environment, healthcare professionals are required to assess, provide, and maintain medication and therapy plans. Thus, providing the app not only for patients but requiring technical integration for healthcare workers loops in professional advice and care. For that matter, organizations aiming to introduce digital SST for customers should consider the affected process in depth to detail where professional or worker involvement is needed or advisable. Then, not only is the introduction of a patient tool relevant, but also the integration of it into existing operations and processes of workers, requiring holistic adoption processes cognizant of hybrid approaches.

V. CONCLUSION

Although automation of work is not a new phenomenon, increasing applications of AI, worker shortages across sectors, and the Covid-19 pandemic have caused drastic changes to service industries and workers. As customers become increasingly digitally savvy, SST empowers individuals to access services online and without human contact. Yet, the impact of SST on service provision from the angle of workers and the role of SST for augmenting work has not yet received much attention. In particular, with debates on automation and augmentation, SST serves an interface at the intersection of service users and service providers. Adding to recent debates, based on most cited and most recent literature, we can see a summary of relevant topics and emerging themes to further explore automation, augmentation, and SST in connection. Contributing to various research streams from management to information systems, innovation management, service management and more, this paper provides incentive to explore automation holistically and understand the role of self-

service for these and future service scenarios. As service, based in human-to-human interaction, and technology continue to transform, new service models will be required and a shift in thinking may be needed. We hope that this paper encourages further research and guides organizations on future applications of SST that empowers consumers and improves employee's wellbeing sustainably.

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